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The Unprepared: A Case Study of Teenage Mothers' Experiences and Child Rearing Practices

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Abstract

Pregnancy complications are far more common in young women. This could inhibit their personal growth and development, take away them of their youth and education, and decline the general health of the country in the process. Focusing on this problem is an ideal matter. Education, family planning, raising community awareness, and teaching adolescents the importance of delaying marriage, reproductive health, and involvement of parents will surely help transform today's teenage girls into healthy, responsible adults who will bear a healthy future generation. The study emphasizes the lived experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and parent's role. Moreover, the study's findings which were based on the Thematic Analysis, were as follows: (1) Teenage Mothers have maternal adjustment difficulties, adolescent reproductive health knowledge gaps, and fear of negative evaluation. (2) Teenage Mothers struggles to discrimination, social rejection anxiety, parenting efficacy, academic disengagement, and financial stress. (3) Lastly, when talking about their coping techniques, Teenage Mothers found support system such as family functioning, where they feel positive, peer influence that uplifts them, maternal identity development through fellow teenage mothers, parent-infant attachment as a source of their motivation, and spiritual well-being where they offer, they overall life to God.

Keywords: *teenage pregnancy, teenage mothers, stigma, family planning, discrimination, support system*

Introduction

Teenage pregnancy is a widespread issue that affects many nations of different economic conditions. It is more prevalent in underprivileged communities around the world, often as a result of poverty, a lack of educational opportunity, and job opportunity. It has a significant role in sexually transmitted infections, intergenerational cycles of poverty and illness, and mother and child mortality (Cabrera & Quesa, 2020). In the Philippines, more than 386,000 or 6.8% of Filipino girls between the ages of 15 and 19 had started parenthood (Young Adult Fertility and Sexuality Survey, 2021). Hence, Philippine Statistics Authority (2022) stated that the majority of young women who were pregnant were aged 19 (13.3%), 18 (5.9%), 17 (5.6%), 16 (1.7%), and 15 (1.4%) respectively. The 8.6% adolescent childbearing rate that was observed in 2017 was decreased by 5.4% in 2022 (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022). Thus, this age group falls under the developmental stage transition to childhood and adulthood between 10-19, which has been distinguished by tremendous growth as well as changes in one's physical, mental, and sociological characteristics (WHO, 2017). In addition, a woman's life is deeply affected by becoming a mother or transitioning to adulthood. Maternal adjustment and sustaining the mother role involves preparation for taking on the maternal role, picking up the right practices, and establishing one's own mother image (Montazeri et al., 2016).

Furthermore, parents are considered to be the most significant figures in the lives of young children. Children learn from birth and depend on their parents along with other caregivers who take on the role of a parent to guide them, take care of them, and help direct them down a path that will promote them as a whole. The parents look forward to seeing their children's personalities develop, well-being. Moreover, teenage mothers are commonly unprepared for the transition of becoming motherhood, the role of parent still plays a significant role in order for teenage mothers to be equipped in this phase. So many also don't know how to best care for them.

Although being a parent is typically a beautiful moment, there are times when parents' lives are complicated and filled with uncertainty regarding their abilities to ensure the physical, emotional, or financial well-being of their children (National Academic Press, 2016).

Furthermore, child-rearing is affected by many factors and many of these are peer pressure (stigma), the media, and parents all provide substantial risks for teenage pregnancy, parents role can help reduce these risks by helping their children make mature, moral, and ethical choices regarding their sexual relations (Silk & Romero, 2013). With this, children who are able to gain benefit from favorable, gentle, engaging, expressive, and authoritarian parenting are the teenagers who also feel stronger security in their connections to their parents are recognized to make sexual decisions thereafter, and are greater susceptible into sexual relations (Aparicio et al., 2018). Additionally, teenage moms are also stigmatized for exceeding parental age expectations and for belonging to socially or racially marginalized groups. The prevention of teenage pregnancy campaigns, media shows, sex education programs, and the public in general all contribute to the stigmatization of young moms and this contributes to the major effect of how a teenage mother may be equipped and prepared for child-rearing (Vinson, 2018).

Several research came to the conclusion that the issue of family relationships and their impact on their children are among the significant contributors to teenage pregnancies and are still needed for further studies about lived experiences, and the role of parents in teenage pregnancy. In the study findings of Grissett (2015) showed that better parental relationships greatly reduced the likelihood that female

and male participants would feel conflicted about becoming pregnant. Contrarily, although there is numerous research that demonstrates a favorable and protective relationship between family connectivity and teenage sexual and reproductive health outcomes, the results still showed no significant relation (Markham et al., 2009, as cited by Sherman et al., 2014). Additionally, in terms of interpersonal and communications, mothers typically perform better than fathers. It would appear that fathers have higher expectations than moms do. The fathers' perspectives are directed toward the outside world; they do not place a high importance on the real daily activities involved in caring for the child (Wills & Beighton, 2017). When compared to fathers, teenage moms showed to contribute more thoroughly and naturally willing to adopt attitudes of openness, listening, and knowing new knowledge and skills (Breinet et al., 2016). Consequently, Velasquez et al. (2023) found that children of single fathers frequently exhibit greater levels of both externalizing behavior (such as antisocial and aggressive behavior) and substance use (such as smoking, drinking, and using drugs) these hindrances make them unable to practice communication, supervision, and monitoring to family functioning.

Moreover, Cripps and Zyromski (2010), as cited by Zubrick et al., (2022) denotes that a lack of parental participation has been significant to lead to risk behaviors, along with that of their delinquent friends, which can lead to sexual activity. However, there are limited studies regarding the knowledge of teenage mothers in child rearing practices and differences of parenting style between teenage fathers and mothers (Wills & Beighton, 2017), such as (1) limited access to and involvement in parenting-related programs and services, as well as the capacity to apply that information to effective parenting techniques, (2) insufficient focus on creating appropriate methods for involving and maximizing fathers' strengths, (3) limited exploration of the influences of fathers' parenting on child outcomes and an understanding of how teenage mothers, fathers, and other guardians work together to support their children's well-being, (4) inadequate understanding precisely how cultures and the implications of discrimination affect practices and beliefs in child rearing (National Academic Press, 2016).

The study sought to explore, determine and comprehend teenage mothers' lived experiences, real challenges, and coping mechanisms and child-rearing practices. Moreover, it explores the factors to be affecting teenage pregnancy. It will emphasize the following concerns such as the significance of child-rearing to a child's development. Furthermore, this study will be used to create an intervention program that addresses teenage pregnancy and improves the decision making of teenage mothers.

Research Questions

The study sought to explain the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms on child-rearing practices of teenage mothers. It particularly sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of teenage mothers on child rearing practices?
2. What are the challenges faced by teenage mothers in child rearing practices?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of teenage mothers in child rearing practices?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed multiple case study approach. In a multiple-case research study, the same phenomenon is studied using two or more cases, or cross analysis between the events. This qualitative approach observes the specific case that each participant faces, such as their life experiences or issues they run into. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews, in which participants offer their responses and additional data, can also be utilized to gather information through case studies. Such as a response to a question on case analysis can result in a case study (Creswell, 2016).

Researchers can explore a particular difference to find a phenomenon that would not be seen otherwise by using the case study approach. The researcher can gain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon and pinpoint the essential elements of these encounters by asking the participants to explain what they have experienced (Moustakas, 1994, as cited in Crawford, 2016).

Respondents

To interview people who had gone through teenage pregnancies, the researcher employed snowball sampling to access this difficult-to-reach group. Furthermore, an inclusion criterion was constructed to identify the limitations of the study.

R.A is a teenage mother who got pregnant at the age of 14 years old. She lives between the industrial and urban areas. Her baby is already 6 months old in the month of August.

She stopped going to school when she found out she was pregnant in 2 months. She has a very complicated relationship with her boyfriend, and she has a broken family. Her mother and father separated when her youngest sibling was only 1-year-old. For her, she is determined and willing to overcome her own battles as a teenage mother.

Jamie apparently became pregnant as a teenager when she was 15 years old. Now a single mother, she works to provide for her only son. Her parents, who are currently caring for her, are assisting her in raising her kid. She is prepared to put in a lot of effort and get back on her feet to support his son's future.

Camille is a teenage mother who became pregnant at the age of 14. She has two children with her live-in partner. Her youngest kid is two years old, while her oldest daughter is five. Her live-in partner works in Pampanga as a casino keeper. She is a housewife, but she is pursuing her dream of becoming a flight attendant by wanting to enroll in classes. So, she is determined to give and fulfill the needs of her 2 daughters.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Participants*

<i>Participant's Codenames</i>	<i>Age of the Participants they got Pregnant</i>	<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>No. of Children</i>	<i>State of Living</i>
Ra	14	Grade 9	1	Dropout/Works as Reseller
Jamiee	15	Grade 10	1	Dropout
Camille	15	Grade 10	2	Dropout/Housewife

Instruments

The study utilized a semi-structured interview guide to gather responses in a methodical and coherent manner. The interview guide's questions were subjected to content validation to confirm their validity. The interview questions were initially some of the teenage mothers who tried to respond, and through the data collection process, the responses were verified in compliance with the research topic and study parameters. An academic consultant conducted the evaluation. Before the interview session with the 3 participants in this study, the instrument was reviewed and updated after it had been accepted.

Data Analysis

There are many methods for gathering qualitative data. Recording and transcribing interviews is one of the simplest strategies to avoid data discrepancies. Interpreting the information obtained from the struggles and experiences of teenage mothers. The original statements made by each participant will be transcribed into the text transcriptions and studied thoroughly.

Sundler et al. (2019) stated that the purpose of thematic analysis is to comprehend the patterns of meanings emerging from data on lived experiences (i.e., the participants' descriptions of experiences pertinent to the research topic in, for example, in depth interviews or narratives). Data that must be textual in nature is used as the starting point for the analysis, which seeks to group meanings into patterns and then themes.

The familiarization with the data through objective listening before starting the analysis. It is necessary to listen to the recorded audio multiple times. The goal of this open-ended interview is to extract the narratives and help readers become more receptive to the text and its implications by putting the openness principle into reality. While listening, the researcher begins to investigate the experiences that are depicted in the data, looking at things like how they are described and how meanings might be interpreted (Sundler et al., 2019).

The process of searching for meanings and themes then strengthens as the various components of the data are progressively revealed. An insightful discussion with the text might be facilitated by switching back and forth between the whole and its pieces. Meanings connected to one another are examined as the study goes along to spot similarities and differences. To recognize patterns, meanings must be connected to one another. Further investigation is done into meaning patterns (Lindberg et al., 2019).

Finally, it must group related topics into an organized whole. Patterns are used to group meanings, and then themes are used. It is useful to compare themes and meanings generated from the original data when generating meaning from audios. It may be beneficial to talk about and think about any potential themes that emerge from the data (Lindberg et al., 2019).

The purpose of outlining the themes is to describe the meanings rooted in the experiences that are being discussed. When the results are presented, they are explained in the opposite order (that is, beginning with the themes and descriptive phrases that are supported by quotes). As a result, participants' experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms and the meanings discovered are conveyed in a thematically arranged narrative (Nilsson et al., 2019)

Ethical Considerations

The research instructor's approval of the method for gathering data and tools confirms that consent has been acquired and that ethical standards have been strictly followed. With the professor's provision, participants who had been chosen and were qualified to participate based on the established criteria were asked to provide full permission via consent form. According to the World Health Organization (2018), minors between the ages of 18 and 19 are considered young adults and have the legal capacity to decide for themselves whether to participate in research. While the term "minor adolescent" simply refers to individuals under the age of 18, or those between the ages of 10 and 18, who lack the mental capacity to make decisions about participation, the parent or legal guardian must make the decision to permit the child's participation in the study with disclosure of privacy rights and limitations.

Full consent had also been discussed while the data gathering process was used. The objectives of the study for the participants' voluntary participation were laid out for them, and they were made aware that they could choose to terminate their participation at any point. They also received the purpose and goals of the study. Participants received assurances that all data collected during the entire study exploration would be used solely for educational and scientific goals, anonymously, and under hidden or make up names.

Discretion is thus protected. Participants are free to give personal details that will remain confidential and will not be disclosed or used in a way that breaches the Data Privacy Act, as required by Republic Act 10173.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the resulting themes and categories in light of the knowledge generated from one-on-one interviews. This also features the analysis and meaning the participants and researchers make out of the experiences related to the phenomena being studied. The succeeding sections are organized in view of the identified cases of the study.

Case 1: R.A

The interview was conducted in the area near industrial on August 14 around 1 pm until 5 pm with rest in between. The interview took only hours wherein we discussed her lived experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and the significance of the role of parents in the life of a teenage mother and as a mother of 6 months old. RA is a determined 14-year-old amidst the struggles she has been through. She showed various feelings and is open to her own experiences without hesitation.

The tables show the themes emerged from the significant statements of R.A about her experiences as a teenage mother.

Table 2. *Thematic analysis of RA's Lived Experiences*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Family Cohesion	Resiliency
Social Stigma	Family Connectedness
Role Strain	Remorse Resolution
Sexual Health Awareness	Self-esteem Reduction
	Maternal Ambivalence
	Parental Exhaustion
	Anticipatory Anxiety
	Impulsivity

RA opened about what experiences and feelings she had in life as a teenage mother and the themes that emerged in the lived experiences are Family Cohesion, Social Stigma, Role Strain, Sexual Health Awareness. Family Cohesion, RA stated that:

"Kaya po nagagawa ko din po siguro yung mga gusto ko at laging nakakagala po at lagi ko din kasama si bf; Si mama talaga ang nakatulong sa akin sa lahat kahit na disappoint ko sya. Laking pasalamat ko din po na kahit nabigo ko si mama eh tinanggap pa rin po nya ako, mas nangibabaw yung pagiging mabuting ina nya rin sa akin." (That is why I can also do everything I want to, such as going along with friends and being with my boyfriend; My mother is the one that really helped me with everything I needed to know. I am grateful to her even though I disappointed her. She still accepted who and what I was. Her love as a mother still endures and overflows).

Some parents experience guilt, believing that they could have prevented this if they had done more to safeguard their children. And while some parents are ashamed that their adolescent is expecting a child and concerned about how friends, family, and Neighbours will respond, others are delighted to learn that they are going to have a grandchild soon, particularly if the teen is older and in a stable relationship. Baney et al. (2022) stated that the crucial factor is that adolescents need parents more than ever. It's critical that people can talk to one another, especially when feelings are particularly considerable. Teenage daughters will experience a better pregnancy—emotionally and physically—if she feels she isn't going to face it alone. Teenagers who carry a baby to term have unique health issues if supported by parents. RA experiences reveal that the situation of family will not dictate your decision to have sex at an early age. Baney et al. (2022) assert that it does not measure your decision making considering you came from a happy family, and you are reaching out. However, guidance by elders or parents is still needed to avoid teenage pregnancy. Supporting your children financially is not enough to be called "supporting" or "guiding children." By encouraging wide-ranging discussions and giving young adolescents access to tools, you can give people the power to decide for themselves what is best for their sexual health.

The second Social Stigma, RA mentions that multiple gossips, judgements, and discrimination by others she was experiencing. This shows that teenage mothers are not safe and do not escape criticism from other people. People will say many negative things about teenage mothers because of the culture and stigma attached to society. Bermea et al. (2018) reveals that teenage mothers are given less favorable treatment than older mothers, and accused of being negligent, irresponsible parents who are "wasting their lives". The third experience is the Role Strain wherein as a teenage mother, RA felt exhausted and confused on some days especially when she doesn't know where to hold on to look for another day. RA mentioned:

"Sa mga unang weeks at days ko po ay yung tulog ko lagi po sira yung tulog ko, lagi din pagod kasi kailangan mo mag pa dede, magpatulog, lalinisan ko sya. Nahirapan po talaga ako kasi hindi naman po talaga ako prepared sa ganitong pagbabago ng buhay ko." (In my first weeks as a mother I always had sleepless nights and was exhausted because I had to breastfeed and clean her up. It's hard for me since I am not even ready for these changes. It's hard to maintain positivity because I am really not okay).

Teenage mothers experience the burden and complexity of motherhood since they must simultaneously complete their adolescent development tasks and fulfill the responsibility of motherhood. They must adjust to the social roles of maturity, the physical changes

associated with puberty, the considerable cognitive growth, and caring for a child (Kagawa et al., 2017).

The last one is the importance of sexual education, awareness, and consequences. RA stated that:

“Ang ideya ko lang ay maagang pagbubuntis, usually po mga teenager’s po. Hindi po yun masyado pinag-aralan o pinag-usapan sa school. Di rin po binabanggit yan ng parents ko kasi nga po sensitibo. Hindi po namin napag-uusapan yung ganyang topic dito sa bahay dahil sensitibo at pang matandang topic lang po kasi yung ganyan.” (My idea about teenage pregnancy is teenagers only. It is rarely discussed in school, or we rarely talk about it. We also do not talk about it inside our home. Even my father does not open things like that because it is too sensitive and adults only talk about things like that).

In order to prevent teenage pregnancy, early marriage, and other problems, it is essential to understand how communication between parents and children works. It is essential to deal with this discussion since there are a lot of misconceptions, stigma, and cultural beliefs attached to society. Not limiting the resources and knowledge will help adolescents to create a smart and safe understanding decision to keep themselves safe from this ongoing issue and help the community build a strong support system to avoid teenage pregnancy.

Table 3. *Thematic Analysis of RA’s Challenges*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Self-esteem Decline	Diminished Self-worth Expectation Burden
Mental Health Resilience	Lack of Mental Support Life Dissatisfaction
Seminar-Induced Learning	Prevention Engagement Cognitive Acknowledgment Financial Capability
Economic Hardship Termination Distress	Financialization of Parenting Abortion-Related Fear

The journey of a teenage mother will never be an easy way, RA comes across a lot of challenges which are put into words such as Self-esteem Decline, Mental Health Resilience, Seminar- Induced Learning, Economic Hardship, Termination Distress. In the study of Linde et al. (2022) women's bodies go through quick changes in size and weight during pregnancy, and these changes happen very quickly. The development of body image dissatisfaction, which has been linked to detrimental health outcomes for both mother and child, may therefore be more susceptible to pregnancy-related risk factors. Women's weight, form, and physical symptoms change quickly as pregnancy progresses, and some of these changes they seem to adjust to while experiencing other changes as negative side effects. Professionals in the medical field should be aware of these risk factors and request them. The development of depressive symptoms, disordered eating patterns, postpartum weight retention, and proven detrimental consequences on children's health are all associated with having a poor body image during pregnancy. Interventions should be designed to address these issues, as RA mentioned:

“Hindi po positive ang tingin ko sa sarili ko araw-araw kasi po kalahati ng isip ko ay hindi ko po tanggap. Kaya po si mama ko lagi naka gabay sa akin sa mga ginagawa ko dahil baka nga po mapabaya ko yung baby ko. Nag iba na po katawan ko, talagang nanay na yung katawan. Imbis na pag aaral ang iniisip ko ay puro kalandian daw. Masakit po sa akin dahil kapag po pala nagkamali ka, parang buong buhay mo na ay mali. Ganun po ang tingin ko lalo na nung buntis ako.” (The moment I found out I have regrets and up until now I still have those, but I tell myself that this is my life. But it doesn't mean that I also want my baby gone. When I look at her, I feel enlightened, but when anxiety hits, it goes back to where I regret things. They said it was part of my post-partum. Instead of focusing on my studies, they said I like to flirt more. It feels like you've been wrong all your whole life. I feel distressed and anxious).

Additionally, Lee et al. (2017) asserts that the support these teenage moms insist on are emotional support, such as comfort, nurturing, and reassurance. Compared to older moms and their non-pregnant friends, adolescent mothers report higher rates of the postpartum period. Different feelings, such as loneliness, anxiety, fatigue, confusion, and transitioning to a new life may still be synced. It's crucial to comprehend some of the emotional phases that pregnant teenagers experience. The emotional and mental stress endured during and after pregnancy can be considerably reduced by acknowledging it and providing assistance. RA stated:

“Siguro po yung nahihirapan ako tanggapin ng buo yung sarili at sitwasyon ko ngayon dahil parang walang naniniwala sa akin or nag chi-cheer up sa akin na magiging okay lang lahat. Parang wala po akong sapat na suportang mental na ngayon. Una palang po na nalaman ko up to now may regrets pa rin po pero sabi ko buhay po ito eh. Pag nakikita ko din yung baby ko, na e-enlighten ako pero kapag tinamaan po ng anxiety at pagka down. Parang dun po bumabalik ulit regrets ko po, sabi nila part raw po ng post-partum ko kaya ako nag ka ganito.” (It's hard to accept myself fully and because of my situation, I feel like no one believes in me or someone to cheer me up that everything will be fine. It seems that I do not get that much support mentally. The moment I found out I had regrets and up until now I still have those, but I tell myself that this is my life. When I look at her, I feel enlightened, but when anxiety hits, it goes back to where I regret things. They said it was part of my post-partum).

Moreover, Dreams (2020) articulate that everyone has an opportunity to educate children about teen pregnancy at a young age so they can make mature decisions about their sexual practice. Children, parents, teachers, health experts, policymakers, and religious organizations are all included in this. The findings show the immediate movement and measures in communities including social

networks and local government can support sex and relationships programmed by providing high-quality, accurate, and engaging teen pregnancy education. This will help reduce the prevalence of unintended teen pregnancies and help open the eyes of both girls and boys to the profound effects that having a child will have on their lives. Thus, the impact of rearing a child should be emphasized to improve the quality of life of teenage mothers who have given birth. In the statement of RA, she mentioned that:

“Pero yung formal na seminar po about sa pregnancy wala pa po. Saka parang wala naman pong mga ganung seminar sa amin. Maganda rin po yun para mamulat po mga ibang kabataan tulad ko sa katotohanan na hindi po madali maging magulang sa murang edad at gaano po kahirap mag alaga at mag palaki ng isang bata. Mahirap din po kasi dahil hindi po namulat sa ganung klaseng topic kaya parang hindi takot na mag resulta sa ganto.” (Our school conducts programs but the formal program regarding pregnancy, they do not conduct. It’s a good program so other teenagers like me will see the reality of how hard it is to become a teenage mother and to care for a baby. It’s hard for me because I wasn’t open to the fact it might result in this. I didn’t feel any fear at that time).

According to RA, providing financial help for teenage mothers was difficult due to its expenses, such as milk, diapers, unexpected check-ups and emergencies since her source of income only came from being a reseller, her mothers’ small sari-sari store, and monthly income of her boyfriend.

“Sapat lang po yung pinansyal namin sa pang araw-araw, nakakakain pa rin naman po tatlong beses sa isang araw pero budget nalang po namin kasi po dami din po na expenses sa anak ko eh.” (Our financial budget is just enough; we could still eat 3 times a day, but we still have plenty of expenses).

“Hindi pa po ganun kalaki, yung kinikita ko din po kasi sa tiktok, at fb hindi rin po ganun kalaki, napupunta rin po sa kailangan namin dito sa bahay at sa anak ko.” (My income only comes to facebook and tiktok and it ain’t enough. I could only get a commission through reselling).

The participant exemplifies that she has insufficient funds for everything and has no stable source of income. She defines that her boyfriend is also an irresponsible father of the child and has no consistency of sustaining monthly payments to their child, even if her partner is working, their pay is low. The access to healthcare services is always provided by the local government everywhere but the only difficulty she faces is the financial income. There are some cases where she needs to take out money for some reasons like medicines. Thus, according to Boateng et al. (2023), teenage pregnancy reduces the likelihood of pursuing higher education, which is a key indicator of financial hardship and poverty. Due to her lack of a stable source of income and her lack of gainful employment, it is evident that the adolescent mother will have financial challenges. Teenage pregnancy is both a cause and a result of poverty.

Table 4. *Thematic Analysis of RA’s Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Adversity Coping	Positive Parenting Spiritual Coping Faith Resilience
Self-Renewal	Social Network Construction
Relationship Enrichment	Supportive Engagement

The experiences and challenges for teenagers’ mothers may be hard for them but this will not measure their determination to look forward to. With these various coping mechanisms narrated by RA, it was themed into Adversity Coping, Self-Renewal, Relationship Enrichment. As stated by RA:

“Sa gitna ng mga pagsubok ko, iniisip ko na matututunan ko din naman paano maging isang responsableng ina sa kanya. Kahit na ‘di maiwasan may marinig na negative sa ibang tao, pasok tenga at labas nalang sa kabila ma’am. Ano ba magagawa nila eh andito na eh.” (In the midst of my obstacle, I always think that I will also learn to be a responsible mother for my daughter. Even though I could never even avoid the chit-chats from other people, I just let it enter my ears and let it go also. They couldn’t do anything, it’s already here).

According to Watson and Vogel (2017) all teenage mothers had to deal with the shame and discrimination that come with becoming a teen mother. However, each person discovered the resilience, optimism, and strength within them to get through those challenges and find a place to fit in. However, it is important to take note that to support a positive outlook of teenage mothers’ lives interventions should be done to achieve a successful motherhood life and as an individual that will aim to improve her quality of life. RA also stated that:

“Gusto ko po ma’am na sumali po sa mga organization na nakikita ko sa tiktok na tumutulong magbigay ng impormasyon sa ibang kabataan tungkol sa usaping teenage pregnancy. Para po hindi lang mabawasan yung ganitong kaso pati na rin po malaman nila paano po ba dapat sila maging prepared sa pagiging ina.” (I would like to join organizations that I see on tiktok, they help spread information to teenagers about teenage pregnancy, this is to prevent cases like this and to know how to become a mother at an early age).

Building social relationships with fellow teenage mothers helps them cope with their own struggles. Relating to one another helps her ease the pain and doubts she has feelings. Moreover, joining programs or non-government organizations that aim to promote the

importance of teenage pregnancy, sexual awareness and education will encourage young teenagers to become responsible for their decision making and actions. Professionals are encouraged to have formal and frequent seminars to discuss the causes, effects and strategies on handling the best situation for teenage mothers as they also struggle with their own mental health conditions.

Furthermore, she also added in her narratives that:

(These happenings to me, I had a lot of realizations of my mistakes and failures that I think I can improve on and look forward to. I am with my daughter, with my mother, and I'm with God. Just rest and pray to God).

Her statement mainly refers to her belief and faithfulness to the Almighty God which gives teenage mothers a chance to be resilient, and hope that will strengthen them everyday amidst all their difficulties, and situations they have been through since the time of their pregnancy and afterward. In addition, having delightness with God improves the lives of teenage mothers when they deal with personal issues such as mental health and “*Kasi ito pong nangyari sa akin, marami po ako na realize sa sarili ko at mali ko na, tingin ko kaya ko mag improve ba at kaya ko ayusin yung hinaharap ko. Kasama ko anak ko, mama ko at nanjan naman si God para sa akin. Pahinga lang po ma'am at dasal sa Diyos.*” physical health, making them stronger than they were before.

Case 2: JAMIE

Now that Jamie is a teen mother, she works to support her kid. To secure her son's future, she is ready to put in much work and get back on her feet. On September 12, 2023, at 11:47 a.m., the interview was held once. In addition to describing her experiences, difficulties, and coping mechanisms, Jamie also discussed the parental role.

The tables display the key ideas that came out of Jamie's important comments regarding her real-life experiences as a teenage mother.

Table 5. *Thematic Analysis of Jamie's Lived Experiences*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Emotional Regulation	Affective Balance
	Parental Adjustment Difficulties
Parental Sacrifice	Difficult Choices
	Selfless Parenting

Jamie discussed how the events contributed to his psychological state and how the themes of Emotional Regulation and Parental Sacrifice came from her life experiences. Thus, Jamie stated that:

“*Mahirap dahil wala pang alam sa pag aalaga ng bata at mahirap dahil sa batang ina ako, walang trabaho, walang pantustos ang aking anak.*” (It was difficult because I didn't know anything about childcare, and it was difficult because I was a young mother without a job and my child had no means of support).

As parents, they wish for a great future for their kids. Dedicatedly strives to obtain income to cover the child's necessities. But in this case, she cannot support her child because she is only a teenager, is enrolled in school, and has a child. She also lacks a great deal of knowledge regarding appropriate childcare. According to WHO (2020), adolescents are frequently unprepared for the realities of parenthood, and difficult relationships, financial burdens, cultural stigma, and parenting can all be stressful, adversely affecting a newborn. It must include education, skill- building, clinical care, and social support for adolescent mothers, young people, and pregnant teenagers.

“*Opo naisip ko ito ipalaglag dahil para hindi masira ang aking pag aaral at the same time para hindi ko mabigo ang aking magulang. Gayunpaman, hindi ko ito tinuloy dahil ayaw ng aking magulang. Mas pinili ko na buhayin at mahal in ang anak ko.*” (Yes, I thought about aborting it because it would not only ruin my studies but also so that I would not disappoint my parents. However, I didn't pursue it because my parents didn't want to. I chose to live and love my son).

Jamie's experience demonstrates that their parents' love for them is still distinct, even in the face of their challenges as teenage mothers. Teenage mothers who get love, support, and guidance can persevere and never give up. They gain a better understanding of how to be a responsible young mother with the assistance of their parents. Regarding communication and attentiveness, parents and their kids usually have significant interactions. Their experiences with parental care, in particular, are consistently the most pleasant, a sign of a healthy connection. Furthermore, they report having honest and comforting familial experiences.

Another means by which kids communicate with their parents or guardians is through listening to them and carrying out their instructions. Teenage parents depended on others when they started parenting and expected support from their mothers, friends, family members, and school training teams.

Jamie faced several difficulties as a young mother, including Parental Efficacy, Financial Distress, Fear of Commitment. In the study of Ramakuela et al. (2016), teenage pregnancy affects young girls' overall health and growth, as well as their studies, feelings, social lives, and the future of society. Family life is directly affected by its weight, which exposes them to health problems and financial instability. As Jamie pointed out, it is indeed challenging to:

“*Napakahirap nang walang alam sa ganito tsaka lalo na kapag walang katulong mag asikaso sa baby ko. Hindi naman pwedeng hindi*

ako tutulong sa kanila sa mga gawaing bahay kasi sobrang nakakahiya naman sa mga magulang ko.” (It is very difficult not knowing about this especially when there is no helper to take care of my baby. It would be too embarrassing for my parents if I didn't assist them with the chores)

Table 6. *Thematic Analysis of Jamie’s Challenges*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Parental Efficacy	Solo Parenting Stress Parental Burnout
Financial Distress	Solo Provider Burden Self-Resilient
Fear of Commitment	Implicit Connections Cognitive Dissonance Survival Motivation

Additionally, Pogoy et al. (2014) discovered that lack of teen pregnancy is a result of sexual education, financial and familial problems, and uncontrolled emotions. After giving birth, teenage moms face various challenges, including having enough money and resources to meet their child's needs. High-achieving adolescent mothers hold jobs and have college degrees to help support their children. Unsuccessful teenage moms become housewives. Young teenage mothers who get pregnant have a lower likelihood of finishing school. They attempted to overcome the challenges they experienced while taking care of the baby and providing financial support. Teenage mothers' capacity to continue their education and succeed is influenced by their academic performance, the support of their families, and their financial position.

“Hirap sa financial. Lalo ngayon, isa na akong single mother kaya kailangan ko talaga mag trabaho nang mabuti para may pambili ako ng mga pangangailangan ng anak ko.” (Financial difficulties. Especially now, I'm a single mother so I really have to work hard so I can buy my son's needs).

Lack of employment is one of teen mothers' most significant issues when trying to afford the supplies needed to care for a newborn or young child. Teen moms rarely work because of school or give up their education, which results in them earning insufficient wages. The ability to financially provide for your child and you are one of the significant worries for teenage mothers. Understanding your primary costs, such as those for food, clothing, housing, transportation, childcare, and health care, as well as where to find financial assistance, can help you budget for these costs and relieve stress. Jamie's third difficulty is fear of commitment when his spouse is irresponsible. As per Jamie:

“Sapilitan nag trabaho dahil walang pang gamot at ang check-up ako noon.” (Forced to work because there was no medicine, and I had my check-up then).

Aparicio et al. (2015) said that their experiences didn't get enough help from their partners, relatives, or medical professionals. Whereas teenage mothers hoped their partners would assist them in all matters pertaining to their children, their lack of assistance was a severe source of frustration. Teenage moms depended on others and anticipated help from their mothers, other family members, friends, and the school training teams as they began their parenting responsibilities. Due to a lack of support, the teenager has struggled with childcare and rearing, child-related expenses, continued education, as well as community involvement.

The last factor is affecting well-being where Jamie stated:

“Maagang nagkaanak, hindi naenjoy ang buhay dalaga, maruming babae, manggagamit na babae. Ayan sa tingin ko yung mga sinasabi sa akin o ayan yung mga salitang inilalarawan sa akin ng iba.” (She gave birth early, did not enjoy the life of a young woman, a dirty woman, a woman who uses women. That's what I think is said to me or that's what others describe to me).

They claim to receive rude looks, inappropriate comments, and low expectations based on common misconceptions (Conn et al., 2018). Teen mothers are eager to demonstrate to others how they are different from the stereotyped teenage moms in order to protect themselves against a "worthless" image. They describe the pregnancy as "accidental" to contradict the accusation of irresponsibility and conceal or tamp down their emotional reactions out of worry that expressing happiness or sadness over the pregnancy or their child would be misunderstood by others (Jones et al., 2019).

Table 7. *Thematic Analysis of Jamie’s Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Self-Perseverance	Self-Image Resiliency Bound and Determined
Sexual Disclosure	Intimate Planning Teaching Efficacy
Embracing Uncertainty	Faith Development Spiritual Coping

Although the teenage mother may face challenging circumstances and difficulties, their drive to move ahead will not be diminished by these difficulties. It was split into themes-based Jamie described several coping techniques: Self-Perseverance, Sexual Disclosure, and

Embracing Uncertainty. As per Jamie mentioned:

“Minsan may nangyayaring ganun, napagsasalitaan ako ng mga magulang ko lalo noong una palang pero tuloy pa rin sa buhay. Hindi ako pwedeng magpadala sa mga salita kasi ako lang din ang tutulong sa sarili ko eh. Kapag hindi ko natulungan sarili ko, paano nalang ang anak ko, diba?” (Sometimes something like that happens, my parents talk to me especially in the beginning but still in life. I can't send it in words because I'm the only one who can help myself. If I can't help myself, what about my child, right?).

In situations like this where they will be addressed, the parents of a teenage mother will not falter, but in the end, they must remain strong for their child. Parents educate their kids to a social environment where they gain self-awareness and a sense of their identity and worth in it. These understandings affect their life decisions and experiences (National Academic Press, 2016).

Jamie also said that:

“Kasalanan sa diyos ang maagang pagbubuntis pero kung hihingi tayo ng kapatawaran sa mga nagawa nating mali na desisyon noon, hindi tayo pababayaan ng Diyos” (Early pregnancy is a sin against God, but if we ask for forgiveness for the wrong decisions we made before, God will not abandon us).

It demonstrates just how unwavering Jamie's faith in God is. No matter how many times he has failed and sinned in the past, he is prepared to repent and ask the Lord for forgiveness for both him and his son. He became stronger through his trust in God, especially after becoming a parent. Jamie also wants to join some programs that discuss teenage pregnancy and how it brings hardship.

Jamie says that:

“Opo para mas lalong maging aware ako sa mga ganitong kaganapan. Mahalaga ito para sa mga may pamilya na para mas lalong lumalim ang kaalaman para sa ganitong programa para makaiwas na rin ang iba sa maagang pagbubuntis.” (Yes, so that I can be more aware of such events. This is important for those who have a family to deepen their knowledge of this program so that others can also avoid early pregnancy).

Siniša (2018), stated that every municipality ought to make an effort to build recreational spaces with robust teen-focused programming. Teenagers sometimes participate in sex because they are bored; therefore, if learners in the communities have sporting and cultural activities to keep them active, they wouldn't have time to consider or engage in sex. With establishing strategic locations like youth clinics, the power of peer pressure would be reduced, and the push for sex education awareness would be strengthened.

Case 3: Camille

Camille is 15 years old currently enrolled in an alternative learning system despite being a teen mother. She is a housewife for her two daughters at the same time. The interview was done on August 25, 2023, at 8 p.m. Camille might highlight the parental role in addition to outlining her experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms.

The tables present the main thoughts that emerged from Camille's significant remarks regarding her actual experiences as a teenage mother.

Table 8. *Thematic Analysis of Camille's Lived Experiences*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Cognitive Restructuring	Stigma Management Teenage Motherhood Adjustment
Subjective Well-Being	External Validation Parenting Knowledge Deficit

Camille explained how the incidents affected his mental health and how her personal experiences inspired the concepts of bravery and affection. Camille responded as follows:

“Takot, kasi hindi ko alam paano ko sasabihin sa magulang ko at kung paano ko haharapin ang mga taong chismosa na ipapakalat na buntis o may anak na ako.” (Fear, because I don't know how to tell my parents and how to deal with gossiping people who will spread the word that I'm pregnant or have a child).

According Cook and Cameron (2015) justified that teenage mothers have a significant impact on a child's growth and character as they prepare them to live a normal life. Since it needs dedication, compassion, incredible perseverance, and a willingness to give up most things in life in order to raise their children properly. In order to forecast success in such a crucial function, extreme maturity is required. Leese (2016) concluded therefore, the majority of adolescent moms do not have strong socioeconomic backgrounds, making the adjustment to motherhood difficult for them to child-rearing practices.

“Hindi ko alam siguro ano, nahihirapan dahil alam ko sa sarili ko na marami pa akong hindi alam tungkol sa pagiging ina.” (I don't know what, so difficult because I know myself, I still don't know how much about motherhood).

Camille's experience shows that despite their difficulties as teenage mothers, the love for their children is evident. Teenage mothers can continue and never give up to support and care for their children. They learn more about what it takes to be a responsible young

mother. Even if they are constantly busy, parents and their children typically have a meaningful interaction when it comes to communication and attention. Additionally, they mention having genuine and encouraging family experiences.

Table 9. *Thematic Analysis of Camille's Challenges*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Financial Health Management	Family System
Mental Health Distress	Family-Well-being Dynamics
	Psychological Well-being
	Body Image Perception

Camille faces many difficulties; being a teenage mother is never an easy path. The idea of Financial Health Management and Mental Health Distress was motivated by her personal challenges.

“Struggle sa financial, stress and depression sometimes anxiety *kapag hindi kami okay ng asawa ko dadamay lahat lalo pagdating sa pag budget hindi magkasya na minsan nagdudulot ng stress.*” (Struggle with finances, stress and depression, sometimes anxiety when my husband and I are not okay, especially when it comes to budgeting which sometimes causes stress).

According to the study of Pogoy et al. (2014) the absence of teenage pregnancy is caused by sexual knowledge, money and family issues and uncontrolled emotions. They face obstacles in caring for the infant and helping out financially, which they attempt to overcome. Additionally, Mengali et al. (2017) says that teenagers had a lot more obligations and a lot more effort to do after having a child. As a consequence, they become exhausted and need assistance and support to raise their children. Most teenagers struggle to keep up with the task, having trouble managing their time and plans.

“*Makaranas ng ptsd pagkatapos manganak.*” (I experienced ptsd after giving birth).

Financial difficulties and exhaustion can affect everyone, including mothers. A study by Javasidar et al. (2016) found that teenage mothers often feel inadequate in their new role, confused, and bewildered. They may feel even more unprepared due to increased expectations. Postnatal year testimonies show newborns' attachment behavior is primarily based on physical needs.

Table 10. *Thematic analysis of Camille's Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subthemes</i>
Social Network	Personal Development
	Social Support
	Optimism
Life Satisfaction	Family Goals
	Achievement Motivation

The adolescent mother may encounter unpleasant situations and challenges, but these challenges won't stop them from moving on. It was divided into themes based on Social Network and Life Satisfaction that Camille articulated. According to what Camille said:

“*Basta magsumikap kami ng tatay ng anak ko alam namin na wala kami pagsubok na hindi malalagpasan at magpatuloy hangga't hindi pa namin na tatamasa ang maginhawang buhay.*” (As long as my daughter's father and I work hard, we can get through any obstacle and keep going until we can love comfortably).

“*Dahil naniniwala ako sa mga positibong bagay lalo na't alam ko na may mga taong nandyan para tulungan ako o makinig kung sakaling may problema kong dinadala.*” (Since I think only good things may come from it, especially knowing that there are individuals who are willing to help me or simply listen if I have a problem).

However, Dankyi et al. (2019) says that depending on the many positions that people play in society, different expectations may exist. Teenage mothers will need to develop coping mechanisms such as altering the structural demands by sharing duties, altering their own expectations regarding their roles, and working extremely hard to achieve all requirements for their roles. discovered that some women utilize taking their children with them as a coping strategy, using paid domestic help, leaving them with neighbors, relatives, or older siblings, or taking them to a daycare center.

In addition, she also narrates that:

“*Kailangan positibo kalang sa lahat ng bagay tiwala sa sarili ang kailangan wag na wag susuko sa problemang dadaan sa buhay.*” (To overcome the challenges, you will experience in life, you must always be positive and full of confidence).

Her statement is mainly based on her conviction that fighting for one's life and the well-being of those they love offers teenage mothers a chance to be strong and gives them hope that will help them work every day despite all the challenges and scenarios they have faced since the beginning. Additionally, having assurance and authenticity makes teenage mothers' life better when they deal with problems in life like their mental and physical health, making them stronger than they were before.

The following table shows the cross-case analysis of RA and Jamie.

Table 11. Cross-Case Analysis of the Emerged Themes of RA and Jamie

Statement of the Problem	Case of RA	Case of Jamie	Analysis Based on the statements of RA and Jamie
<p>What are the lived experiences of teenage mothers and on child rearing?</p>	<p>Family Cohesion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resiliency • Family Connectedness <p>Social Stigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remorse Resolution • Self-esteem Reduction <p>Role Strain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maternal Ambivalence • Parental Exhaustion <p>Sexual Health Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipatory Anxiety • Impulsivity 	<p>Emotional Regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affective Balance • Parental Adjustment Difficulties <p>Parental Sacrifice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult Choices • Selfless Parenting 	<p>The statements of both cases of RA and Jamie have shown the similar experiences in terms of struggle to mental health and emotional being and both of them have encountered confusion, and worriedness in the motherhood life. Moreover, they highlight the found support systems from their parents.</p>
<p>What are the challenges of teenage mothers on child-rearing?</p>	<p>Self-esteem Decline</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diminished Self worth • Expectation <p>Burden Mental Health Resilience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Mental Support • Life Dissatisfaction <p>Seminar-Induced Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention Engagement • Cognitive Acknowledgement • Financial Capability <p>Economic Hardship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financialization of Parenting <p>Termination Distress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abortion- Related Fear 	<p>Parental Efficacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solo <p>Parenting Stress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parental <p>Burnout Financial Distress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solo Provider Burden • Self-Resilient <p>Fear of Commitment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implicit Connections • Cognitive Dissonance • Survival Motivation 	<p>The cases of RA and Jaime emphasize the various similarities of challenges on self-concept and society putting so much pressure with their physical features affecting their life. Additionally, financial struggle and distress is the most challenging among them as they are incapable of having a stable source of income. They also pointed out the fear of committing early pregnancy due to the stigma attached in society about teenage pregnancy.</p>
<p>What are the coping mechanisms of teenage mothers?</p>	<p>Adversity Coping</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive Parenting • Spiritual Coping Self-Renewal • Faith Resilience <p>Relationship Enrichment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Network Construction • Supportive Engagement 	<p>Self-Perseverance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-Image Resiliency • Bound and Determined <p>Sexual Disclosure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intimate Planning • Teaching Efficacy <p>Embracing Uncertainty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faith Development • Spiritual Coping 	<p>Both of their responses pointed out how much distress, confused, intimated, and embarrassed they have experienced. With this, RA and Jamie have found ways in coping with these challenges and experiences. One, it is essential for them to cope through having a fighting spirit and ignoring those negative people so that their anxiety will not get worse. Secondly, praying to God or having faith are their ways to remain positive and to find strength in Him. Lastly, building good, healthy relationships and educating are the most significant ways for them to forget the mistakes made by them and try to educate other people so that this case will not happen again.</p>

The table below shows the cross-case analysis of RA, Jamie, and Camille.

Table 12. *Cross-Case Analysis of the Emerged Themes of RA, Jamie, and Camille*

<i>Statement of the Problem</i>	<i>Analysis based on the statements of RA and Jami</i>	<i>Case of Camille</i>	<i>Analysis based on the statements of RA, Jamie, & Camille</i>
What are the lived experiences of teenage mothers and on child rearing?	The statements of both cases of RA and Jamie have shown similar experiences in terms of struggle to mental health and emotional being and both of them have encountered confusion, and worriedness in the motherhood life. Moreover, they highlight the found support systems from their parents.	Cognitive Restructuring <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stigma Management Subjective Well-Being <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teenage Motherhood Adjustment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External Validation • Parenting Knowledge Deficit 	These cases of teenage mothers, it shows that all of them encounter the struggle of transition of motherhood wherein they have limited knowledge and are confused about their situation. Their response summarizes the impact of living with fear of judgement which affects their overall health.
What are the challenges of teenage mothers on child-rearing?	The cases of RA and Jaime emphasize the various similarities of challenges on self-concept and society putting so much pressure with their physical features affecting their life. Additionally, financial struggle and distress is the most challenging among them as they are incapable of having a stable source of income. They also pointed out the fear of committing early pregnancy due to the stigma attached in society about teenage pregnancy.	Financial Health Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family-Well-being • Family Stress Mental Health Distress <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychological Well-Being • Body Image • Perception 	Three of the teenage mothers have shown the most challenging part as teenage mother wherein they all have to deal with discrimination and negative comments about their own physical appearance every day. In addition, the lack of knowledge in child rearing is also shown to be a challenge by RA, Jamie, and Camille as they all have to stop going to school when they get pregnant. It is crucial that completing education is an advantage to properly nurture a child, especially when learning and skills are shaped in school. Findings showed that three of them are in need of financial Struggle in continuing their education as it will bring much expense to them.
What are the coping mechanisms of teenage mothers?	Both of their responses pointed out how much distress, confused, intimated, and embarrassed they have experienced. With this, RA and Jamie have found ways in coping with these challenges and experiences. One, it is essential for them to cope through having a fighting spirit and ignoring those negative people so that their anxiety will not get worse. Secondly, praying to God or having faith are their ways to remain positive and to find strength in Him. Lastly, building good, healthy relationships and educating are the most significant ways for them to forget the mistakes made by them and try to educate other people so that this case will not happen again.	Social Network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Development • Social Support Life Satisfaction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimism • Family Goals 	These three teenage mothers have overcome the difficulties and challenges and maintain positive outlook on life. All of them have similar coping strategies. First is having a support system like families, fellow teenage mothers, friends, and having God by their side. They manage to maintain a positive, happy life, and remove anxiety in them by talking to people they feel are welcomed, beautiful, and worthy. Secondly, they all cope with their baby when things are falling apart. For these teenage mothers, their babies are their blessing, the source of strength and inspiration to look forward to in life. Lastly, they all have given up their mistakes and failures to God, they are motivated to make things right again by having wisdom and peace every day of their lives.

The instances mentioned above of teenage mothers highlight the everyday experience of grappling with the challenges associated with the transition to motherhood. These young women often need more information and clarification about their circumstances. The participants provide a concise overview of the consequences associated with lived experiences, it includes Maternal Adjustment Difficulties, Adolescent Reproductive Health Knowledge Gaps, Fear of Negative Evaluation significantly influencing their general well-being. Secondly, three adolescent mothers have encountered the most formidable aspect of their experience as young mothers, wherein they confront often and themes emerged as Discrimination, Social Rejection Anxiety, Parenting Efficacy, Academic Disengagement out who are compelled to discontinue their education upon becoming pregnant, and Financial Stress which was exemplified by RA, Jamie, and Camille. Moreover, they indicated that education completion is an utmost important matter fostering a child's development, particularly in acquiring and refining knowledge and abilities within the school environment. Furthermore, the

study results indicated that three individuals require financial support to pursue their education, which entails so much costs.

These three teenage mothers have conquered obstacles and adversities while maintaining an optimistic perspective. All individuals have comparable coping mechanisms. One crucial factor is a support system, which may include Support System such Family Functioning, Peer Influence, Maternal Identity Development where they can cultivate a sense of positivity and happiness in their lives while also alleviating feelings of worry by engaging in conversations with individuals they see as being welcoming, pleasing, and of inherent value. They also cope with their Parent

Infant Attachment. For teenage mothers, their babies/child represent a profound source of joy, serving as a wellspring of resilience and motivation for the future. Spiritual Well-Being is their coping strategy wherein each individual has handed over their mistakes and shortcomings to the Lord, inspiring them to rectify their actions and cultivating wisdom and serenity in their daily existence. Lastly, all individuals manage their babies/child throughout times of distress and sadness.

Conclusion

This study focused on the various dimensions of teenage motherhood and their approaches to parenting, which have received limited attention in previous research and have yet to prioritize an analysis of mental state and lived experiences. The conclusions that may be drawn from the findings of this study are as follows:

1. Teenage mothers felt a sense of embarrassment and hesitation in talking sexual/reproductive education. This is because the absence of parental communication between parents and teenage mothers is also a factor why teenage mothers become pregnant at an early age. The majority of adolescents and their parents did not engage in an in-depth discussion regarding sexual matters. A few brief discussions may have transpired, primarily containing cautionary statements such as "beware" and "you're too young." The parents often instigated and directed the short and infrequent dialogues to the recurring embarrassment of the children.
2. It is a big struggle to teenage mom to keep their finances balance, they often experience distress, among other things, a lack of receiving financial support due to being an adolescent mother brought by their electricity bill, food supplies, baby necessities, emergencies, limited income, and the avoidance of commitments from their partners.
3. Teenage mothers face prejudice because of their age. Physical appearance is a significant aspect; body image expectations have a role in their mental health problems. When a mother feels compelled to maintain her appearance under societal beauty standards, it can lower their self-esteem and affect mental health. Moreover, they also felt fear and intimidated by other people.
4. One of the findings indicates that adolescent mothers possess a restricted understanding of child-rearing. The primary perspective of the individuals in question concerns the importance of providing adequate care and instilling values in their children. This viewpoint is influenced by their decision to discontinue their education, resulting in a limited acquisition of information, facts, and skills that may be obtained through experiential and formal learning. The fundamental underpinning of a child's developmental trajectory and overall welfare is in the capacity of an adolescent mother to provide instruction and guidance to her child from infancy through the early stages of life.
5. Teenage Mothers felt discouragement or low self-esteem when they are faced with so much discrimination, and negative comments from people or fellow teenagers as well as they are worried about financial because they are incapable to support their education because of prioritizing what matters first.
6. Young teenage mothers solely rely to God through praying as a result of their unintended pregnancies, and challenges as young mothers. They felt optimist, gratitude, and hopefulness in their safe-paced. Additionally, God as being the center of teenage mothers' life helped them coped and ran against from negative public opinions.
7. The findings demonstrate how important support systems such as families, friends, fellow teenagers, and local community. It is found that support systems have a significant impact on teenage mothers to look forward positively in their lives and persevere when they are supported mentally and emotionally. Therefore, building positive relationships substantially linked to better outcomes for teenage mothers to reduce anxiety and distress, thus, they are educated by others knowledge of sexual/reproductive health.

After carefully analyzing the results of the study, the identified several key recommendations are:

1. It is highly recommended that the schools in basic education should be willing and able to reach out to parents in conducting a seminar that will encourage them to participate in the discussion of reproductive health education. Educators and Guidance Counselors must believe that it is proper for them to involve parents and feel secure in their ability to do so. By providing excellent learning opportunities and resources to help schools and teachers involve parents might make significant progress in this area. Importantly, this engagement process of parents and schools should work together to promote positive sexual and reproductive health. Schools may play this role by offering comprehensive, evidence-based reproductive-sexual health; thus, parents can have a positive approach to share their own experiences, values, beliefs, and expectations.
2. It is highly recommended that the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DWSO) or Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) establish a law for teenage mothers to receive constant financial assistance in supporting their continued education. The

financial difficulties of everyday living and necessities that young moms face make it harder for them to return to school. The organizations are essential in breaking the cycle of persistent vulnerability and inspiring individuals to follow their goals. Thus, by providing various/intervention program which aim to persuade the young mothers to return to school so the mothers will feel optimistic about their future.

3. It is highly recommended that professionals such as psychologists work with the LGU program services that will address concerns related to the stigmatization and unlawful discrimination against teenage mothers who are pregnant or parenting.

4. It is highly recommended that Local Government Unit (LGU), and TESDA with the help of Barangay prioritize a program service connected to social work in providing information for child-rearing and development, improving healthcare, and livelihood training, increasing the pregnancy prevention intervention, family planning, mental health and legal aid, and student mentorship.

5. It is highly recommended that Guidance counselors to work and collaborate with Barangay to evaluate and track the psychological health of the teenage mothers through individual and group counseling. By extending awakenings as well as motivation, this can help them continue their aspiration, improving skills and learning through going back to school.

6. It is also highly recommended that faith communities help offer Christian Counseling, holistic care, educational sessions about sexual/reproductive health education and even family planning services within the context of their faith traditions. A strong case can be made that providing such information in the context of personal faith and spiritual values can be very effective.

7. It is highly recommended that teenage mothers should be strongly supported by support systems like family members, friends, fellow teenage mothers, and the local community. They are capable of pursuing their dreams. These people should be the main source of mental, emotional support, and encouragement of teenage mothers especially when they feel excluded in society.

8. Future researchers may also explore the child-rearing practices, state of living, background of their family, and parenting strategies of teenage mothers. In this way, various approaches may help them to make parenting more convenient. In addition, the study's findings are highly recommended as a source of information in exploring the teenage mother's experiences and child-rearing practices.

9. It is highly recommended that a counseling program for teenage mothers wherein comprehensive initiative designed to address the emotional, educational, and parenting needs of young mothers. Licensed professionals will be encouraged to provide assistance to this process. The program integrates individual and group counseling sessions to enhance emotional well-being, parenting classes for skill development, academic support, life skills workshops, and peer mentorship. Focused on holistic well-being, it also incorporates health and fitness components, community engagement, and regular evaluation for ongoing improvement. By providing a supportive environment and tailored resources, this program aims to empower teenage mothers, fostering their personal growth, educational pursuits, and successful parenting journey.

10. It is highly recommended that a sustainable livelihood project uniquely crafted for teenage mothers to foster economic empowerment and self-reliance. This encompasses skill development workshops tailored to individual interests, offering training in areas like crafting, tailoring, baking, or digital literacy. Complementing these skills, entrepreneurship training equips participants with the knowledge to launch and manage small businesses. This supports the establishment of microenterprises, providing initial funding and resources. In addition, to enhance market access, the project facilitates online platforms and imparts digital marketing strategies. Community pop-up markets create opportunities for teenage mothers to showcase and sell their products, fostering local support and community engagement. A mentorship program pairs participants with experienced mentors, ensuring ongoing guidance and support. Moreover, it is a holistic approach to building sustainable businesses and empowering teenage mothers for a brighter future.

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